

The W-STEM Data Collection Survey: Extracts and Notes

W-STEM institutional data collection survey

Leena Pääsky OULU University

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INSTITUTIONAL BACKGROUND INFO

INSTRUCTION: Please provide information on formal structures that could provide some insight on institutional purpose i.e. special activities and policies. These questions on programmes, staff and students will help us to understand the context.

PROGRAMMES

INSTRUCTION: Mark all ISCED-F 2013 variants that you offer programmes

P.1. Which programmes / courses are you using for data collection, by field of study?

P.2. Do you have unique multidisciplinary STEM programmes that intend to attract especially female students?

P.3. Length of programmes (years / months)

What kind of universities are taking part in the W-STEM project?

What type of programmes form the basis for the data analysis?

05 Natural sciences, mathematics and statistics								
051 Biological and related sciences		052 Environment		053 Physical sciences			054 Mathematics and statistics	
0511 Biology	0512 Biochemistry	0521 Environmental sciences	0522 Natural environments and wildlife	0531 Chemistry	0532 Earth sciences	0533 Physics	0541 Mathematics	0542 Statistics

Which level of the ISCED-F 2013 was used during the data collection?

Were there other type of classifications in use regarding the STEM fields?

Was it possible to offer disaggregated data?

06 Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs)			07 Engineering, manufacturing and construction											INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING	OTHER	
061 Information and Communication			071 Engineering and engineering trades					072 Manufacturing and processing				073 Architecture and construction			OTHER	
0611 Computer use	0612 Database and network design and administration	0613 Software and applications development and analysis	0711 Chemical engineering and processes	0712 Environmental protection technology	0713 Electricity and energy	0714 Electronics and automation	0715 Mechanics and metal trades	0716 Motor vehicles, ships and aircraft	0721 Food processing	0722 Materials (glass, paper, plastic and wood)	0723 Textiles (clothes, footwear and leather)	0724 Mining and extraction	0731 Architecture and town planning	0732 Building and civil engineering		Please specify

4. STAFF

INSTRUCTION: Fill in the total and share of female staff by field of study (STEM-variant of ISCED-F 2013):

4.1. Provide the total number of teaching staff members for first year of programmes in your university by field of study in 2018.

4.2. Provide the total number of female teaching staff members for first year of programmes in your university by field of study in 2018.

4.3. Provide the total number of staff trained on gender issues in education.

4.4. Provide the total number of female staff trained on gender equality issues in education.

Related policies:

4.5. What, if any, training on gender issues education does your university provide for its staff in STEM programmes?

4.6. What, if any, benefits does your university provide for its staff advancing their gender competence?

Teachers play an important role as models for students at all levels of education.

Description: The teachers of the STEM programmes

Situation assessment: The training of staff on gender issues

5. STUDENTS

INSTRUCTION: Fill in the total and share of female stUDENTS by field of study (STEM-variant of ISCED-F 2013)

5.1. Provide the total number students by field of study in 2018 in your institution.

5.2. Provide the total number of female students by field of study in 2018.

Description: The students of the STEM programmes

6. ATTRACTION

INSTRUCTION: Fill in total and share of female applicants to university by field of study (STEM-variant of ISCED-F 2013)

6.1. Provide the total number of applicants for first year of programmes in your university by field of study in 2018.

6.2. Provide the total number of female applicants for first year of programmes in your university by field of study in 2018.

Related policies:

6.3. What, if any, policies, processes and activities does your university implement as part of its attraction campaigns for STEM programmes?

6.4. What, if any, policies, processes and activities does your university implement as part of its attraction campaigns specifically for female applicants for STEM programmes?

Overview: How interested are women to apply to study in STEM programmes?

The attraction campaigns for STEM fields: What role do the women have?

7. ACCESS

INSTRUCTION: Fill in total and share of female students accepted to university programmes by field of study (STEM-variant of ISCED-F 2013):

7.1. Provide the total number of applicants accepted (i.e. offered a place) onto first year of programmes in your university by field of study in 2018

7.2. Provide the total number of female applicants accepted (i.e. offered a place) onto first year of programmes in your university by field of study in 2018

Related policies:

7.3. What, if any, policies, processes and activities does your university implement to encourage applicants for STEM programmes to access?

7.4. What, if any, policies, processes and activities does your university implement to encourage female applicants specifically for STEM programmes to access?

Overview: Do female applicants get accepted to the STEM programmes?

The encouragement of applicants to access:
Special attention given to women?

8. ENROLLMENT

INSTRUCTION: Fill in total and share of female students enrolled to university programmes by field of study (STEM-variant of ISCED-F 2013):

8.1. Provide the total number of applicants enrolled (i.e. accepted and took a place) on first year of programmes in your university by field of study in 2018

8.2. Provide the total number of female applicants enrolled (i.e. accepted and took a place) on first year of programmes in your university by field of study in 2018

Related policies

8.3. What, if any, policies, processes and activities does your university implement to encourage applicants for STEM programmes to accept and enrol once offered?

8.4. What, if any, policies, processes and activities does your university implement to encourage female applicants specifically for STEM programmes to accept and enrol once offered?

8.5. A brief description of the student selection at your university with a specification if there are quotas or other measures aiming to influence to gender balance.

Overview: How many of the accepted applicants enrolled?

The encouragement of applicants to enrol:
Special attention given to women? Quotas for women?

14. DISCRIMINATION

INSTRUCTION: Fill in total and share of female encounters of reported discrimination events during the year 2018 by sex of reporter; education level; and field of study (STEM-variant of ISCED-F 2013):

14.1. Total number of reported discrimination events during the year 2018 by sex of reporter; ethnic background; education level and field of study of educational programme.

14.2. Total number of female encounters of reported discrimination events during the year 2018 by sex of reporter; ethnic background; education level and field of study of educational programme.

Related policies:

14.3. A brief description of the discrimination prevention / intervention procedure at your university.

How sensitive are institutional practices, practitioners and fellow students and are there grievance procedures at place?

Summary: the reported discrimination events

Description: discrimination prevention and intervention procedures at different universities

15. SEXUAL HARASSMENT

INSTRUCTION: Fill in total and share of female encounters of reported sexual harassment events during the year 2018 by sex of reporter; education level; and field of study (STEM-variant of ISCED-F 2013):

15.1. Total number of reported sexual harassment events during the year 2018 by sex of reporter; education level and field of study of educational programme.

15.2. Total number of female encounters of reported sexual harassment events during the year 2018 by sex of reporter; education level and field of study of educational programme.

Related policies:

15.3. A brief description of the sexual harassment prevention / intervention procedure at your university.

How sensitive are institutional practices, practitioners and fellow students and are there grievance procedures at place?

Summary: the reported sexual harassment events

Description: discrimination prevention and intervention procedures at different universities

47. GUIDANCE (modified nbr 9)

INSTRUCTION: Fill in total and share of female graduates from university programmes by field of study (STEM-variant of ISCED-F 2013):

47.1. Provide the total number of applicants who enrolled in first year in your university in 2018 who successfully completed first year by field of study

47.2. Provide the total number of female applicants who enrolled in first year in your university in 2018 who successfully completed first year by field of study

47.3. Provide the number of students in your university who graduated in 2018 by field of study

47.4. Provide the number of female students in your university who graduated in 2018 by field of study

Related policies

47.5. What, if any, policies, processes and activities does your university implement to support and guide students on STEM programmes through their studies to encourage retention and graduation?

47.6. What, if any, policies, processes and activities does your university implement to support and guide female students specifically on STEM programmes through their studies to encourage retention and graduation?

Summary:

The completion of the first year

The graduation figures

Description: The support and guidance on STEM programmes at different universities – specific processes regarding women?

48. DROP-OUTs (NEW)

INSTRUCTION: Fill in total and share of female drop-outs from university programmes by field of study (STEM-variant of ISCED-F 2013):

48.1. Total drop-out at first year

48.2. Share of the female drop outs during the first year (2018-19)

Related policy:

48.3. A brief description of the student drop-out procedure at your university with a specification if there are preventing measures at place.

Overview: the drop-out figures

Description: The drop-out procedure and prevention at different universities

Disclaimer

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